

Transition pathways – towards sustainable trade

MATS Deliverable 5.2

MATS

making agricultural trade sustainable

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Summary

The work within task 5.2 in WP5 started in M27 (September 2023), according to the work plan schedule in the Description of Action in the GA. The aim of the task is to jointly develop transition pathways towards our MATS vision presented in D5.1. Building on the results from the visioning process options for action towards the shared vision were formulated and elaborated in a workshop with MATS partners and external stakeholders. The workshop was held during MATS project meeting in Brussels. In preparation of the workshop four online meetings (February 2024, described in D5.1) were organized to involve a broad spectrum of stakeholders in the compilation of actions.

This deliverable summarises the approach taken to jointly define actions to reach the MATS vision and presents the selected actions. The combination of actions can contribute to transition of agricultural trade towards more sustainability. Policy recommendations to enable the implementation of actions will be formulated in task 5.3.

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¹ R = Report, P = Prototype, D = Demonstrator, O = Other

² PU = Public, CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Transition pathways – towards sustainable trade

Background

As there is a need for a systemic approach in agricultural trade policy analysis, a roadmapping approach was adopted to facilitate a shared understanding of goals, timelines, and activities (Galvin 1998; Kerr und Phaal 2020; Park et al. 2020). The methodological approach co-designs this process in a targeted way.

We want to work towards a more sustainable and resilient food system with economic and trade partnerships where partners recognize each other as “equals” (Juncker, 2018).

The applied methodology also bridges individual case studies to a global context, helping translate localized insights into a broader context. The process to formulate transition pathways for desirable changes in agricultural trade relations towards greater sustainability began with a participatory visioning process to envision future directions towards the shared aim for the MATS members (internal process). During the whole process, it became apparent that despite their differences, overlaps among various case studies emerged, highlighting shared objectives for sustainable trade.

After describing desirable changes in trade regimes, trade relations and instruments for the time horizon 2035+ including all partners with their on-the-ground insights (see D5.1), the second step was to define concrete actions leading to the accomplishment of the different vision statements. It incorporated both internal insights and external perspectives, from outside the MATS project, from various agri-food chain stages. This co-creation step ensured a comprehensive approach.

To ensure constructive discussions, the big question was broken down into thematic bundles using the four previously defined sustainability dimensions – “policy, governance and regulation”; “social and human dimensions”;

“natural capital”, and “economy and markets”. To enable a reflection of the formulated vision statements and to identify a comprehensive set of actions leading to these desired states, four online meetings allowed stakeholders from the case studies to propose actionable steps (see D5.1).

The actions not only aim at realizing the desired vision but also shape the policy recommendations as the project evolves. Some of them are specific to one dimension, while others address all four dimensions of sustainability. The findings revealed a need for both innovative and existing policies that address sustainability comprehensively, advocate for decentralization, and reduce bureaucracy to support smallholder farmers in accessing markets and obtaining fair prices.

Approach

After the series of webinars a comprehensive set of actions was gathered addressing the various vision statements. First ideas for action were already collected in the context of the visioning workshop in Moshi/Tanzania. Further actions from literature were summarized and presented in the series of webinars (February 2024), providing additional insights for formulating actions that were discussed during the process. The aim of the webinars then was to discuss and refine all previously formulated actions, identify further actions and strategically assign them topic and time wise in the roadmap (see D5.1). After this, the actions were consolidated within the WP5 core team to arrive at a clear wording and avoid duplications.

The actions identified earlier formed the basis for discussions during the Workshop held in Brussels in March 2024. This workshop brought together consortium members, case studies, and external experts to critically select and discuss the most crucial actions. The discussions took place in a World Café setting, structured around the four key dimensions of sustainability: Social and Human Dimension, Natural Capital, Economy and Markets, and Policy, Governance, and Regulations, which led to the formation of four tables, accompanied hosts to inform the following groups about the discussion. This enabled that all participants could contribute to all topics discussed. This work resulted in 34 actions presented below.

FIGURE 1: OVERVIEW OF THE STEPS OF FORMULATING TRANSITION PATHWAYS

Results

Main discussion points

As described above the discussion on actions was coordinated in four working groups according to the dimensions of sustainability. In the following a short summary is given of each of this working groups followed by the total list of identified actions.

The dimension of 'policy, governance and regulation' tried to make connections in to the other three dimension of sustainability. In the discussion it was pointed out that the theory of change suggests that improved dialogue among actors leads to greater policy coherence only when there are incentives involved. Policies affecting the social and human dimension should emphasizes the inclusion of small-scale and female farmers in dialogues and calls for targeted sustainability incentives. In the realm of natural capital, creating safe spaces for activists, promoting agro-ecology, and connecting subsidies to environmental performance should be in the foreground. When tackling economy and markets, the focus should be on the need for fair access to sustainable standards and practices. It is proposed that sustainability should benefit companies, demanding accountability and participatory decision-

making from large investors in relation to small-scale farmers. Together, these perspectives underline the necessity of incorporating diverse viewpoints and ensuring equitable, transparent dialogues to drive policy coherence.

The main discussion thread in the group on social and human dimension was that the approach to achieving sustainable development should include three main pillars: ensuring living incomes and wages, promoting fairness and sustainability, and supporting small-scale farmers and marginalized communities. Firstly, policies aimed at securing living incomes and wages must consider potential unintended consequences, such as increased child labour. Secondly, reducing the gender gap is crucial for establishing fair and sustainable practices. Thirdly, empowering small-scale farmers and marginalized communities involves providing resources like knowledge, co-creation opportunities, capacity building, financial support, and access to land, with the effectiveness of cooperatives being contingent on good governance within them. To successfully implement these pillars, a comprehensive regulatory framework is necessary, alongside significant changes to business models and sourcing practices.

The group discussing topics connected to natural capital pointed out that the future of digital agriculture focuses on individual farmers adopting technology, which includes the potential benefits and challenges such as information security concerns caused by digitization, and the use of ICT for early warnings about environmental events like droughts and floods. Regarding the impact assessment of trade agreements, critiques suggest that frameworks like Economic Partnership Agreements (EPAs) and Free Trade Agreements (FTAs) should involve more active participation from local stakeholders and consider human rights impacts. Furthermore, there is a suggestion to provide loans for contract farming to support agricultural business models. These diverse elements highlight the multifaceted approach needed to address the challenges and opportunities within the agricultural sector.

In the last group on economy and markets it was highlighted that the discourse on international monitoring and compliance mechanisms for investments and trade agreements emphasizes the necessity for standardized environmental impact assessments that integrate environmental, human rights, social, and labour standards. These assessments should be conducted both before and after projects, and require joint efforts for broader

acceptance, focusing on significant investments and involving local communities. Enforcement of outcomes is a crucial missing component. Additionally, there is a push to incentivize and upscale voluntary sustainability standards, ensuring they complement rather than replace existing policies and encourage bottom-up approaches. Knowledge sharing and capacity building are advocated to adopt sustainable agricultural practices, emphasizing the importance of utilizing diverse and local knowledge systems, facilitating horizontal knowledge exchanges, and leveraging digital tools and extension services. The significance of consumers and dietary patterns in sustainability is subject to debate. While some consider it a minor focus, it is still acknowledged as an important component in the wider discussion on sustainability.

34 MATS actions

The 34 actions to reach the jointly developed vision are named and shortly described in the following. Due to the participatory process and the World Café setting, all participants of the series of webinars (see D5.1) and the workshop in Brussels contributed to the formulation of actions and their final selection.

Develop and Disseminate Sustainable Water Management Guidelines:

Develop and widely disseminate guidelines for sustainable water management practices in agriculture, ensuring efficient irrigation methods, water conservation, and proper treatment of wastewater. Provide training and support to farmers to implement these guidelines and adopt sustainable water management practices. Promote water-efficient farming practices to reduce water waste and absolute water use. Encourage the implementation of water recycling and reuse systems in agricultural operations. Promote the adoption of nature-based solutions for water allocation in agriculture to ensure compliance with environmental regulations, focusing on enhancing productivity while preserving environmental integrity.

Establish International Environmental Monitoring and Enforcement:

Establish an international monitoring and enforcement mechanism to ensure compliance with environmental regulations, including those related to biodiversity conservation and sustainable farming practices. Collaborate with international organizations and governments to develop and implement standardized monitoring and reporting frameworks for environmental performance.

Launch Consumer Awareness Campaigns on Environmental Impact:

Launch consumer awareness campaigns to educate and inform the public about the environmental impacts of their dietary and consumption habits. Promote sustainable and responsible consumption practices through targeted messaging and initiatives that encourage reduced meat consumption and support deforestation-free industries.

Establish Climate Risk Insurance for Farmers: Establish insurance and re-insurance programs specifically tailored to farmers to mitigate the financial risks associated with climate change-induced natural disasters. Advocate for policies and incentives that promote the availability and accessibility of insurance products for farmers, including flexible payment options and exchange mechanisms.

Implement Policies to Prevent Deforestation and Promote Conservation: Implement policies and initiatives to prevent deforestation linked to agro-ecological practices, such as promoting sustainable land use and forest conservation. Strengthen global value chain governance to account for biodiversity considerations, ensuring that supply chains prioritize biodiversity conservation. Support farmers, especially small-scale farmers, in preserving agro-biodiversity through training, access to diverse seed varieties, and sustainable farming methods.

Develop Sustainable Farming and Biodiversity Programs: Develop and implement agro-ecology programs that promote sustainable farming practices, focus on social issues and local content, and support food security and incomes. Establish institutionalized frameworks and support systems for agro-ecology, providing training and resources to farmers to adopt sustainable practices and conserve biodiversity. Launch knowledge-sharing platforms and training programs for farmers, intermediaries, and consumers to promote the adoption of best agricultural practices and enhance consumer awareness and understanding of sustainable agriculture.

Promote customers' awareness for faire trade and livelihoods of producers: Implement and promote fair trade certification and labelling programs to establish standards for fair pricing, working conditions, and environmental sustainability in supply chains. Encourage consumers and businesses to support fair trade products through awareness campaigns and

incentives, fostering a market that values and supports the livelihoods of producers.

Develop Policies for Diversification in Supply Chains: Develop policies and initiatives that promote competition and diversification of suppliers within importing markets, reducing the dominance of centralized markets. Provide support and resources to local businesses and producers to enhance their competitiveness and expand market access, for example by reviewing, simplifying and streamlining existing bureaucratic processes and regulations.

Support Value-Addition Activities in Third Countries: Support value-addition activities in third countries through technical cooperation (or even reversing tariff escalation). Furthermore, increasing capacity building at farm-gate would enable more transparency, thereby supporting inclusive horizontal governance that builds on local private and public governance actors, including NGOs. They should be commodity and country-specific.

Conduct Impact Assessments of Trade Agreements: Conduct comprehensive impact assessments before and after trade agreements to evaluate their effects on local markets, poverty levels, environment, and food security. Use the findings from impact assessments to inform policy decisions and negotiate trade agreements that prioritize sustainable development and poverty reduction.

Explore and Promote Digital Agriculture Opportunities: The potential of digital agriculture to empower smallholder farmers as opposed to increasing the divide between farmers and intermediaries (i.e., market power asymmetries)

Support Producer Associations with Training and Resources: Provide training programs and resources to support smallholders in forming and strengthening producers associations or cooperatives, enabling them to overcome administrative hurdles and increase competitiveness. Streamline administrative processes and reduce paperwork for smallholders to make it easier for them to participate in cooperatives.

Enact Legislation for Corporate Sustainability in Supply Chains: Enact legislation that mandates chocolate and other companies to conduct comprehensive analyses of their purchasing practices' impact on living income

and take necessary actions to ensure fair compensation, for example a mandatory requirement for the inclusion of the cost of a living wage in product prices. Establish regulatory mechanisms and penalties to enforce compliance with HREDD obligations and hold companies accountable for their impact on living income, possibly by publicly identifying and exposing companies engaged in unethical practices in their supply chains, raising awareness, and promoting consumer boycotts.

Encourage Participation in Certification Schemes: Encourage farmers and agricultural businesses to participate in voluntary certification schemes that promote environmental objectives and ensure compliance with sustainable practices. Provide financial incentives and technical assistance to support the implementation and maintenance of certification schemes, including training and capacity-building programs. Facilitate obtaining and maintaining certification for sustainable and quality production by creating dedicated funding mechanisms or grants and exploring partnerships with financial institutions and impact investors.

Facilitate Sustainable Agri-food Investments: Facilitate partnerships between foreign private-sector investors and agri-food actors in developing countries to provide the necessary financial resources for sustainable development aligned with the SDGs. Create investment funds specifically targeted at supporting sustainable practices in the agri-food sector.

Improve Food Cold Chain Logistics: The performance and scale of FCCL must be improved to minimize food loss and waste.

Establish Price Observatories in Agricultural Supply Chains: Establish price observatories at different stages of the agricultural supply chain to monitor and analyse price changes, providing valuable information for market participants. Collaborate with relevant stakeholders to ensure the transparency and accessibility of price observatory data, enabling informed decision-making.

Enact Local Market Allocation Legislation: Enact legislation that requires companies involved in exporting food products to allocate a certain percentage of their production for the local market, ensuring food security and availability for local communities. Implement incentives and support programs to

encourage companies to prioritize domestic market supply when exporting food products.

Introduce Legislations to Transform Business Models: Analyses on food system transformation tend to frame measures as a win-win for people and planet when there are actually many trade-offs. Consider the specificities of the context and keep in mind the complex relationships across various geographical scales (local, regional, global)

Integrate Gender Perspective in Corporate Due Diligence: Integrate a gender transformative approach into companies' human rights due diligence (HREDD) processes, conducting risk assessments that consider and address gender-based vulnerabilities and discrimination. Develop gender-specific measures and interventions to promote gender equality and empowerment within value chains.

Advocate for Fair Wage Policies: Advocate for the implementation of fair wage policies and regulations that ensure farm workers receive living wages, such as the establishment of a minimum price guarantee for agricultural products. Encourage companies to commit to paying living wages to farmers and farm workers through voluntary agreements or certification schemes.

Develop Sustainability Standards for Small-Scale Producers:

Develop and enforce sustainability standards and legislation that specifically consider the impact on small-scale producers and cooperatives, ensuring that compliance burdens are primarily placed on larger companies in the value chains. Strengthen the role and position of cooperatives as key stakeholders in value chains through policy measures and support programs that enhance their capacity and bargaining power

Cultivate Sustainable Food Systems through Knowledge Networks:

How local community food systems can respond to pressure from global problems like hunger, chronic health conditions, fluctuating food costs, appropriation of land, etc. Support of local knowledge networks by supporting small-scale farmers and local value chains is both important and necessary to the cultivation of sustainable food systems.

Raise Sustainability Standards in Value Chains: For value chains to be sustainable, they have to be fair. They should be aligned with supply and

demand, globalized but also domesticated. Raising minimum sustainability standards and promoting voluntary action, especially for companies that are not consumer facing, is necessary to achieving fair and sustainable value chains. Particular focus should be on due diligence policies and supply chain law; promoting fair and sustainable agricultural trade with multi-actor and -level actions, alongside targeted actions and investments.

Promote Inclusive Collaboration and Governance: Common methods are often established by a small set of actors and may exclude other stakeholders (e.g., sub-national governments, indigenous peoples, local communities, etc.) Collaboration is key to identifying the most successful approaches to sustainable practices and for accountability. Rural communities, indigenous groups, women, youth, other minority groups have limited agency to influence decision-making. Develop governance mechanisms to empower them. Provide information and capacity development for meaningful engagement.

Enforce Corporate Accountability: Enforce existing laws and regulations based on the UN guiding principles on business and human rights, ensuring that companies are held accountable for their actions and impacts. Develop and implement national action plans that outline specific measures and requirements for companies to conduct human rights due diligence (HREDD) in their operations and supply chains.

Facilitate vision alignment on all levels: Institutional reform towards greater policy collaboration of domestic institutions to address the complexity of combining the trade, climate and nature agendas. Work towards a shared vision on the regional level (e.g. East Africa), continental level (e.g. African Trade Union), and the local / community level, as well as towards global agendas.

Facilitate Dialogues with large agricultural traders: Facilitate policy dialogues and engagement between large agricultural traders, particularly with influential traders such as China, to discuss and promote the evolution of social and environmental trade standards in their respective markets. Foster collaboration and knowledge sharing to drive positive change in global agricultural trade practices.

Align Sustainable Investment with Local Policies: Align sustainable investment strategies with local development policies and global value chains,

reducing over-dependency on external markets and resources; encourage investments in value-adding activities closer to the farm gates, such as processing and packaging, to increase the value of agricultural product. Develop transparent and accountable investment guidelines and criteria that prioritize environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors.

Re-purpose Agricultural Subsidies: Many agricultural practices are actually harmful to the planet but are made attractive by government subsidies (e.g., the overuse of fertilizer and agrochemicals, unsustainable land expansion, and skewed income distribution). The funds for these should be repurposed towards subsidies that do not harm the planet. This is to avoid 'locked-in' economies in certain production methods.

Build Local Capacities for Sustainable Trade: Establish capacity-building programs and initiatives that focus on knowledge exchange and skill development for farmers and intermediaries in sustainable trade. Allocate funding and resources to support the creation of local institutions that promote trust, transparency, and knowledge sharing among stakeholders in the trade value chain. Develop training programs on future markets, labelling regulations, and other relevant topics to enhance the capacity of farmers and intermediaries to engage in sustainable trade practices.

Enhance Interconnectivity of Food-System Initiatives: Increase interconnectivity of food-system-oriented initiatives to maximize their impact on strategic policy-making. Initiatives address various legislations and policies. Therefore, concerned policies must be effectively coordinated to facilitate joint actions. This will result in the comprehensive and wide-ranging implementation of food-system initiatives.

Alignment of policies to simultaneously target multiple dimensions of sustainability: Different dimensions of sustainability must be addressed simultaneously. Complementary policies (to trade policies) that target specific aspects of sustainability should be implemented.

Reform and Integrate Food System Policies: Transition to sustainable food systems requires both new and old policies. An effective sustainable food policy requires new policy goals, frames, and mixes, as well as new approaches for evaluation. Improving existing policies means improving coordination and the involving new actors at different scales; they can be

scaled-up and integrated with other tools to become more impactful. Necessary new policies must encompass stronger involvement of civil society and urban municipalities, as well as multilevel governance and the participation of relevant stakeholders to be effective.

Roadmap

In the following, a roadmap visualises the actions connected to their respective vision statements and assigned time wise.

FIGURE 2 LEGEND FOR THE ROADMAP

FIGURE 3: ROADMAP TO ACHIEVING SUSTAINABLE TRADE

Infographics

To illustrate certain aspects of the collected actions a set of infographics was developed. Additional infographics will be designed for the brochure on transition pathways, which will be presented at the MATS final event.

FIGURE 4: PROMOTE INCLUSIVE COLLABORATION AND GOVERNANCE

FIGURE 5: DEVELOP AND DISSEMINATE SUSTAINABLE WATER MANAGEMENT GUIDELINES

FIGURE 6: ENCOURAGE PARTICIPATION IN CERTIFICATION SCHEMES

FIGURE 7: ENHANCE INTERCONNECTIVITY OF FOOD-SYSTEM INITIATIVES

Follow-up

The results from D5.2 will be passed on towards Task 5.3 and Task 5.4 on the feasibility of changes in trade relations and recommendation for improving trade regimes, respectively.

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